

From e-Government to e-Democracy Challenges and Opportunities for Development in Montenegro

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Abstract—Internet today has a huge impact on all aspects of life, and also in the area of the broader context of democracy, politics and politicians. If democracy is freedom of choice, there are a number of conditions that can ensure in practice the freedom to be achieved and realized. These preconditions must be achieved regardless of the manner of voting. The key contribution of ICT to achieve freedom of choice is that technology enables the correlation of the citizens and elected representatives on the better way than it was possible without the Internet. In this sense, we can say that the Internet and ICT are changing significantly, and potentially improving the environment in which democratic processes are taking place. This paper aims to describe trends in use of ICT in democratic processes, and analyzes the challenges for implementation of e-Democracy in Montenegro

Keywords—About four key words or phrases in alphabetical order, separated by commas.

I. INTRODUCTION

GOVERNMENTS around the world have realized that transformation from traditional government and traditional management to electronic government is the most important public policy issue of our time. But whether the story has become a reality? Actually, what is the real story?

e-Government doesn't include only implementation of new information and communication technologies (ICT). It refers to changing business models and processes with aim to enable different and efficient business processes. IT provides a solution, but e-Government refers to changes in the way government agencies operate. Being "eReady" and managing the transition to e-Government will not happen by itself. This is a very complex process and requires careful and concrete actions. Governments around the world want to set leading edge and challenges in e-Government visions that others will follow. In response to these activities, government agencies are making many efforts to "switch" work and operations of public sector in the era of computerization. For example, a significant number of public sector representatives have set up a central web portal, which has constantly being upgraded. And at the level of agencies, many government agencies around the world have had their own web sites, which expanded over time by placing the focus on activities such as electronic services delivery (ESD) [4].

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At first, this may sound very impressive, and basically it is. But challenges and changes are so great and expectations of the governments are so large, that such steps are only the beginning of many major initiatives and activities.

For example, during the establishment of its ESD targets, agencies may be tempted to choose a service that can quickly be available online, as opposed to those that can generate the most overall benefits. Of course, there is nothing wrong with this approach, but it is often more important to start with the implementation of e-Government solutions, and achieve results quickly. The long, slow and expensive mega-projects in general can be described as projects that help the advancement towards e-Government.

However, the risk of reaching quick initial goals is that neither agencies nor community will be impressed with what these results are offering. Unfortunately, the greatest value lies in areas that offer much greater challenges.

In order to be present online as soon as possible, regardless of the values and needs, and functionalities, there is satiety of websites in many strategies for performing and creating e-Government. During this process, it is often forgotten the key fact of what e-Government has to offer, as well as to community and to agencies. Many agencies and institutions in charge clearly see that such activities only slightly »scratch on the surface" and that they need a clear reform process in order to assure all the changes that the government wants to undertake.

So, what are the next steps? What are the key factors that must be identified to lead the implementation of e-Government?

To implement e-Government vision and initiatives, or to make agencies "e-ready" for progress, some obstacles that must be avoided have been identified. These obstacles are divided into 8 categories, namely: (1) leadership and governance, (2) funding, (3) people, (4) legal, (5) customer readiness and accessibility; (6) privacy, (7) security; (8) technology and information management [7].

For many governments ESD is a priority in their e-Government strategies. Their goal is to deliver better, faster, more reliable and cheaper services to business sector and the community. A very important part of this strategy is the development of government agencies web sites through which government services and information may become available, at the same time enabling citizens to interact with governments. Significant efforts have been taken during creation of these websites, knowing that potential benefits of

ESD will not be realized unless the web sites are not user-friendly.

Realizing previously stated the question arises: How much are government Web sites user-friendly?

- Are the services and information needed by businesses and citizens available on the site?
- Is it possible to access and find information and services easily, irrespective of whether users are in rural areas, or if they are visually impaired or have limited skills in the official language;
- Which level of technology skills are needed to access these sites;
- Which level of interactivity is required, etc.

II. GOVERNMENT 2.0

Early development and breakthrough of e-Government - use of information and communication technologies in order to provide and improve public services, transactions and interactions - has enabled government agencies to provide better service and improve efficiency and effectiveness. For example, in many countries, more than 70% of people pay taxes electronically, and many other transactions - from renewing driver's licenses and payment of the parking lot to the management of government benefits - can be implemented and carried out online.

In any case, despite continuous allocation of a large number of sources, progress in the field of e-Government in recent years has "become straight" (appears to have plateaued), in relation to how it used to be. Many of the new e-Government initiatives have generated expected interest among customers on one side, or allowed the clear benefits in operational efficiency, on the other. Whether it comes to unexpected fiscal constraints, or the high expectations of users based on the integration of the Internet in their daily life and work, the imperative is exactly the fact that the public sector improves their access to eGovernment in order to ensure that these initiatives will achieve the greatest impact.

As shown in practice, three obstacles have restricted the influence of e-Government efforts: ineffective management, lack of supported web capacity and not allowing the participation of users in the process of creating applications and content [7].

To reach the next level of e-Government services, organizations must overcome each of these obstacles. First of all, they have to move it to the management model in which the e-Government initiatives are owned "by line of business" executors and supported by respective cross-functional teams. Secondly, they must develop the capacity and capability in critical areas such as marketing, usability, Web analytics, and access into customers. Finally, government agencies must change their mindset to proactively gain citizens, businesses, and other agencies involved in providing contributions or creating applications and content.

Implementing these changes will enable public sector organizations to provide Web services that will use a large number of users much more easily, reduce development costs

and management services over time, provide greater functionality and content, thus providing a higher reimbursement of spent funds.

Creating new governance models - Agencies need to understand Web development as an integral part of services provided to voters - along with initiatives such as call centres or regional units and offices. Web projects need to be managed through a consolidated portfolio with a centralized views and understandings of the costs and benefits. Clear end-to-end ownership of online experience must be established and strengthened, with responsibilities relating to the level of acceptance by users and costs.

Management of e-Government projects must be based more on data collection and data management. Organizations must establish balance between the benefits of implementation of security decisions and cost restrictions, including the financial impact and effects of usability, comfort and acceptance. When an agency discovers that its web team, IT team and security team each have different conceptions of legal and security demands, it will clarify the requirements and enable defining specific responsibilities. The team in charge of security will be granted full responsibility for access to security, while the web team will be assigned responsibility for understanding the safety requirements that affect usability and deciding where to invest and what functions / features should be run.

Investing in Web capabilities - Effective web management does not require the formation of large teams, but must include a key group that is well informed about the requirements of business processes that are concerned with and related to customers, fact-based decisions, usability and navigation, marketing, information architecture and agile web development.

Agencies can identify the gaps in their capacity and set goals through the development of scorecards that show a category of facilities and activities to which each individual is covered. For each activity that is displayed, the agencies are supposed to specify detailed criteria for team members that they will use as the basis for evaluating their current performance and establishing targets for improvement.

Adopting "open innovation" and user participation - the process of strengthening governance and capacity will not only improve the existing content and services but will also help lay the foundation for the continuation of Web 2.0. technology. The shift from "publishing" to the sharing of experience - which includes the participation of all users - must be done in cooperation with and within government agencies. Some agencies (nationwide) are leaders in this field.

Government can use Web 2.0 technologies to move the barriers between and within organizations. How the change of ways of thinking can be achieved to enable the Web 2.0 initiatives to be divided among several government agencies? Leaders of agencies, both those who are engaged in business policy, and those who deal with IT policies, must accept innovation and participation coming from a third party. They need to talk and discuss the benefits of these efforts carry with them, to encourage the taking of risks, and

to increase the capacity of their staff in implementing these initiatives.

III. WEB 2.0 VS. E-GOVERNMENTS 2.0

e-Government is already for many years in all development policies of countries and at EU level it was a priority in development policy since the eEurope Action Plan in 1999 and until today, until the latest version of e-Government Action Plan.

Since 2003., the new wave of web applications, which are all placed under one name web 2.0, is running with very little investment, and recorded a dramatic success in the initial stages of application operations. These applications are based on users as producers: of content (blogs, wiki, Flickr), taste/emotion (Last.fm, de.li.cious), contacts (MySpace) and reputation/feedback-a (eBay, TripAdvisor). Web 2.0 is a term used to describe the development of the Web in a way which enables collaboration and communication in the process of service delivery, in contrast to the previous environment in which the Web is primarily used as a one-sided channel for publishing content.

Recent studies of the influence of these technologies emphasize striking effect that they already have in social life of the people, as well as industries such as advertising and media.

There are many definitions and the names of Web 2.0 (social software, participatory web, user generated content, etc.), each of which represents one dimension and excludes others. One of the definitions of Web 2.0 is that it consists of a set of technologies, applications and "values." From the technological point of view, creating blocks of Web 2.0 applications are the innovations that were introduced several years ago in order to affect the increase of use/utilization, integration and reuse of Web applications.

The key question, in order to support the development of e-Government policy, is whether these trends are relevant and whether they have any influence on the activities related to the work of government, and modernization of state administration. In order to obtain answers to this question, IPTSI made a report to support the development of e-Government and contributed to the development of EU policy in this area.

Further, the following questions may be asked [7]:

- Are web 2.0 applications relevant for the content of governments?
- If so, in which direction Web 2.0 may have an impact on governments?
- How important can be this influence?
- How are web 2.0 applications implemented in governments and how much are they relevant to their content?

There is considerable evidence to indicate that these applications are very important for the development of e-Government services and more, in different domains of e-Government. These applications can much more contribute to the realization of important objectives in terms of creating a

better, simpler, more transparent, connected and networked governance. All this affects the creation of a positive influence of individual web 2.0 projects; of course, the full impact is not done, given that these projects are still in early stages of implementation. Also, it is well known that the evidences about the effects of ICT are usually visible only after a few years of investing.

Users can contribute to improving public services and they are already working on that. This does not mean that all citizens will participate and contribute, but some will. Furthermore, even weaker forms of participation can be useful for the improvement of services [8].

Although there are strong elements of a different understanding of concept of Web 2.0, many emphasized socio-economic trends make us think that key features are not just a passing fashion but part of larger changes. Today's teenagers will quickly begin to work and will become part of the workforce and/or will become users of government services. In addition, long-term trends of user empowerment, creative knowledge workers, global competition, various forms of work organization, and user-oriented innovations are appropriate, and enabled with Web 2.0 applications.

This should encourage governments to start experimenting with these applications. Most applications are free or cheap, which makes the process of experimentation easier. The question is not only the acceptance of technology: creating blogs or wikis on the government's web sites will not by itself strengthen the participation of citizens. Instead, it should be moved towards more open and transparent relationships with customers, including the value of web 2.0. As already shown, these solutions are implemented through the mechanisms of tests and errors, as well as through an iterative development through a "beta" version. This learning curve includes also the work on relevant government mechanisms that ensure that user involvement is compatible with the overall role and objectives of the governments.

This does not mean that public administration must fully accept/embrace web 2.0 in all its e-activities: other methods and applications are necessary in some important areas of business such as interoperability, privacy and security. Web 2.0 is also a tool that enables the achievement of public goals; it is a complement and does not replace existing e-Government initiatives. In addition, there are significant risks with which governments need to confront, such as destructive behaviour, interference, and low quality of services and content.

But as said before, the citizens and businesses already use this application in relation to the activities of government, and in this sense, governments are not in a position to decide whether this application should be used to provide public services. As project manager on one project said "the key is risk management, not risk avoidance."

In this sense, experimenting and inclusion of these applications is not only a potential benefit, but probably the safest options for governments.

IV. E-DEMOCRACY

On the Forum on the Future of Democracy, held in Madrid in 2009, where the issue was e-Democracy, one of the key questions was what is e-Democracy. Secretary General of the Council of Europe, Mr Terry Davis, in his speech offered an answer to this question by saying: "I do not think there is anything that can be called electronic democracy, the same way as paper democracy does not exist. There is democracy on paper, of course, but it's another question. We can talk about e(lectronic) voting, eCampaign, eAdministration or any other eWord you can imagine, but democracy is simply a democracy "...

However, information and communications are now in the centre of any cultural, economic and political activities in the broadest sense. Media significantly affect the way of the adoption and implementation of political decisions at local, national or international level. In addition to radio and TV, the most widespread and influential medium is the Internet, and therefore a frequently used sentence saying that we live in an era of electronic communications and the Internet is justified.

ICT and the Internet are rapidly becoming key tools that enable not only access to information but multiply communication channels that extend the possibilities of Internet far above the performance achieved to date. So it raises the question of elementary (internet) literacy of modern man, as a precondition for any serious engagement with any activity. Today Internet has a dramatic impact on all aspects of life including the area which is within the broader context of democracy and politics and politicians. If democracy is the freedom to choose there are a number of conditions that need to be fulfilled in practice for this freedom to be achieved. These preconditions must be met regardless of the way of voting – it is not important is it done by ballot or by pressing buttons on a computer, mobile phone or „voting machines“. The key contribution of ICT to achieve freedom of choice is that the technology enables the correlation of the citizens and elected representatives in a much better way than it had been possible without the Internet. In this sense, it can be said that the Internet and ICT significantly changed and potentially improved the environment in which democratic processes are taking place.

Digital Democracy can be defined as a democracy that reflects the information age, where the ICT, especially the Internet have provided a far greater and better access to government agencies and information for citizens, allowing rapid exchange of information between large numbers of people - thus promoting non-governmental organizations, citizens' associations, etc. Digital Democracy implies the use of ICT to strengthen the power of democracy, particularly as a tool that allows citizens to directly participate in policy making. It should be able to unite the possibilities of new communication environment that has the power to increase the quality of a participation in management processes. The development of e-Democracy will have important effects, and it will facilitate the revitalization of society by enabling citizens to focus their thoughts and ideas and involve them in decision-making process.

e-Democracy includes:

- eAdministration - refers to the electronic management of state affairs management
- Information management - refers to the creation of effective communication between citizens and decision makers
- Populist model or the model of "electronic city services" - allows citizens to electronically publish their own views on certain issues.
- The model of civil society - refers to the transformation of political culture with the help of communication technology, which should affect the quality of public debates and change in interpersonal relationships
- Model of agreement democracy - this model allows the establishment of online forums for discussion between politicians and citizens through the process of representation and expertise, and which citizens are resolving immediately.
- The model combining representative and direct democracy - implies that citizens represent the values and they decide which issues require resolution through the process of representation and expertise, and which citizens are resolving immediately.

Although still not sufficiently tested, the area of e-Democracy needs to strengthen democratic and political life of the state by using ICT.

When it comes to the critical point, the total success of e-Democracy depends largely on building trust of citizens and institutions in technology, first of all having in mind terms like security, safety and confidentiality. The issue of protecting privacy rights, intellectual property, etc. will become more important, especially in countries where regulations remain inadequate or have not been enacted. Gaining trust of voters in the robustness and privacy which the technology is supposed to ensure is also one of the critical points of success of e-Democracy.

V.E-DEMOCRACY MODELS

Representatives of the Academy and others have conducted the research about the e-Democracy models. Organization for European Cooperation and Development (OECD) has defined three types of interactions in e-Democracy - providing one-way information, two-way relationship in which citizens have the opportunity to provide feedback on certain issues, and finally, a partnership in which citizens are actively involved in decision-making process. Similarly, Coleman and Götze [10] propose four scenarios. The first is technological support to a direct democracy. Second covers the widest layers of online social communities of interest. The third refers to the online survey and discussion groups. The fourth refers to the technology as a way to encourage and engage citizens in policy-making. Gartner Dataquest has developed a model on four levels in the area of "eDevelopment", which can be applied to services to citizens and to e-Democracy. On the first level (presence) Internet site provides information online in a static format. On the second level (interaction), the citizens search the information, download forms, or access via links to other relevant sites. The third level (transactions) facilitates

the need for completing transactions by mail or by visiting the offices. The fourth level is transformational. Some of the attributes of this level are wireless access, providing information about government operations through the web sites as well as rough CRM tools. A very important feature in this case is the redesign of working capacity and business processes.

The Institute for e-Government (IEG) provides models of e-Democracy and go further when it comes to the definition and implementation of e-Democracy (Picture 1). IEG model is not limited to citizen-to-government point of view, marking and displaying the progression of the aspects of information and inclusion of citizens. It serves as a scorecard of digital skills - how well the government unit interprets and reacts to the environment in the digital world and how successfully they use technology in line with progressive influences. This "entity" can be either selected representative, or legislative body, local or state governments, political parties or international organizations. The model helps leaders to find a way in which they can jointly embrace and integrate tactical and strategic efforts of e-Democracy and create e-Government strategy. With one step, governments can identify their current position with the appropriate characterization of the different levels of sophistication, and find a solution about the eInitiatives that can take them to the next level. One axis measures the level of involvement, and the second axis measures impact.

Fig. 1 e-Democracy model [9]

First Quadrant - Passive, one-way, asynchronised - Most government bodies - governments, legislative bodies, international organizations, political parties - have done a very good job of making that information available online. This represents an important step in the development of e-Democracy.

Legislation bodies began to realize that it is not only the question of how to use technology to communicate with voters, but how it is done in the style of modern business, using technology.

Second quadrant - two-way, asynchronised, tactical - The entities in this quadrant have made a big step forward in facilitating two-way communication.

If we approach it in terms of users, the question is who is in fact the "government"? As mentioned in the movie

Ghostbusters „Who are you going to call?“ - is it the municipal president, the government or the parliament? Could it be the minister of health, tourism, legislation? Or is it perhaps a member of a state agency, the Secretariat, etc.

The correct answer is actually 'all of them!' We all live in the provinces, municipalities, cities, state, and ... the world! And the challenge is reflected in this fact. Every public institution and those who work in that institution are obliged to "move" towards the adoption and increasing use of information and communication technologies and to "open" and establish two-way channels of communication in the era of digital values in which we live.

The third quadrant - collaborative, interactive - This quadrant has more interactive possibilities. Although it is still very asynchronised, communication begins to develop in collaboration/cooperation. The most visible at this stage are the political players and the electoral process with tactics such as registration and organizing volunteers online, online fundraising, campaigns, communication with the voters and the media, voter registration and voting.

The fourth quadrant - Interactive, Strategic - Management of policy-making is not nearly like product lifecycle management. Previously, in the policy-making cycles, more citizens were able to influence the results. Hansard Society in the UK is trying to develop mechanisms for the promotion of public consultation and adjustment with its constitutional processes, by demonstrating the true relationship between public input and results of policies that must be found. They identify and highlight 5 actions that governments have to do: (1) improve the quality of policies through the identification of wider sources of expertise under conditions of increased complexity, (2) prepare for greater and faster interactions at the request of the information society, (3) integration of public input/public opinions in the decision making process and creating law, (4) reaction and positive response to calls for ensuring transparency and reliability, (5) strengthening of trust in government. [11]

This quadrant represents the highest level of sophistication of e-Democracy, if nothing else then to predict the future and expectations - a strategic, interactive, synchronized and global in nature. Today, democratic institutions must at least actively manage the initiatives in this area. If there is any doubt that the leading governments are already using technology to gather input from citizens and businesses in order to time determine the direction of activities, what is needed is to visit only a couple of web sites and thus to identify and define trends.

VI. E-GOVERNMENTS AND E-DEMOCRACY IN MONTENEGRO

By the end of 2006 the Government of Montenegro began the implementation and in June 2007 completed and implemented a project of the electronic session of the Commission for economic policy, one of the Government Commission. Following the good experience that the project demonstrated in maintaining of the electronic meetings, which maximized efficiency, reduced costs and time of preparation of paper documentation for the ministers, members of this commission, it has been implemented a

project for the electronic sessions of the Commissions and the Government of Montenegro as a whole.

The aim of the project was to create and establish a system for electronic support of the Government of Montenegro operations. The idea was to develop and fully establish a system that will facilitate the preparation and operation of the Commissions and the Government of Montenegro meetings, based entirely on electronic documents and web technologies. The system is primarily supposed to be a show case of the use of information technologies in Montenegro and as such is supposed to give some impetus to a further development of information technologies in the same.

In addition to the primary goal, which is implemented, the system has allowed fulfilling of the following objectives in the future:

- Directly to receive electronic documents,
- Use of digital signatures in the exchange of electronic documents, with the establishment of certification bodies, and a systems for issuing of the digital certificates in order to identify the users and to raise the system itself to a higher level of protection,
- Establishing the direct communication between the government bodies using ePortal,
- Expanding the portal to a level at which it will be able to provide a services of e-Democracy.

The structure and complexity of the portal is multiplied and can be divided into a several sub-portals. Functioning of the sub-portals can be seen as dependent units that participate in the session and preparing the sessions of Commissions and Government of Montenegro. This structure consists of: Ministry Portals, Archive of the Secretary General, Portal of Commission on Economic Policy and Financial System, Portal of Commission for the political system and the Government Portal.

In addition to these structural units of the division of the portal, which practically correspond to the hierarchical structure of the institutions of Government portal for the Government electronic sessions is also divided according to the interface for the access to the portal. In fact, apart from the standard access to the portal and its contents, there is a simplified interface through which participants (ministers and others) on the actual sessions of the Commission and the Government can effectively access the contents of the portal.

VII. CHALLENGES AND OPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPMENT OF E-DOMOCRACY

One of the challenges of information society development lies in raising the quality and availability of the Internet in different regions, especially in those areas where it is not profitable for the private sector to invest. In any case, the use of the Internet depends not only on the availability of infrastructure, or costs of the service, but, to a considerable extent it depends on the motivation - ie. existence of useful and necessary content and awareness of the existence of the chances that the information society offers. So, although it is very important for Montenegro to provide online services,

more important is to enable citizens to use those services, as well as to create an environment in which citizens and companies understand the necessity of using them. When those requirements are met, it is necessary to further strengthen trust and improve services in the spirit of modern information and communication technologies.

One of the important issues of modern society is the development of inclusive society, which requires building the trust in electronic communication channels. Confidence in the Internet and motivation towards the use depends on the skills of the people themselves on how much they use computers and electronic services. It is very important to understand that ICT does not only create chances for solving the bottleneck problems, but provides additional opportunities for participation in public life (e-Democracy), for a continuous, flexible and personal development (eLearning), entertainment and so on. Similarly, one should bear in mind that today more than half of non-Internet users does not intend to start using it. In order to avoid further creation of the digital divide between those who have access to Internet and to electronic services and those who do not, the provision of public services should be provided and secured through a system with multiple channels[10].

In addition to citizens, it is necessary to pay attention to the private sector, and in this sense, increasing efforts to improve the understanding of the influence of ICT on economic activity in companies. Understanding of impact of importance of ICT on entrepreneurship and the economy generally, is not only challenge of the companies themselves and the business sector, but also of the public administration. In this regard, studies that measure and analyze the impact of ICT on economic growth and development should be increased.

ePortal for electronic meetings of the Commissions and electronic meetings of the Government is only the beginning of government initiatives towards the development of information society, and is associated with the development of e-Democracy in Montenegro.

In order that activities related to creation of information society become successful, it is necessary to fulfill a number of factors:

- Enable citizens and businesses to use information technology,
- Provide them access to all and in all regions, at very favorable terms,
- Increase public confidence in the processes of public administration,
- Increase the level of public confidence in the direction of respecting their views and opinions etc.

ePortals are a good basis for the development of e-Democracy initiative. These portals need to be enhanced to a level at which citizens will be able to propose topics and materials that will be considered by members of the Government, and in this way will create a situation in which "can be heard the voice of the people."

When it comes to e-Democracy, one of the main indicators is the participation of citizens in decision-making processes or eParticipation. The easiest way to get citizens involved in decision-making processes, is to create an environment in which they will be able to:

- Follow the processes of decision making, adoption of laws and the like,
- Send comments regarding the law and material,
- Suggest interesting topics or current issues whose resolution will later be the obligation of the ministers,
- Vote for a material or an interesting topic etc.

Any of these proposed elements of eParticipation will not be realized if there is no legal basis, both in the regulation of institutions and in various other materials relating to the operation of ministries and other agencies.

One of the courses of e-Democracy development in Montenegro, particularly in the case of the Government of Montenegro, may be toward improvement of ePortal in a way that allows citizens to send their own ideas, materials, any problems or anything about what they want to inform the Ministry or the Government for what they think that is relevant to the community.

One of the critical factors that will occur in such cases is to define the limit of the necessary number of votes that would allow any ideas and any problem to become required for the ministry to include in its agenda during the session. In the initial stages of development of the portal for eParticipation, this level may not be fulfilled, but it is very important to allow citizens to give a vote for an idea or problem in order to get the impression that it is really important to them. Every idea, and every material that will have more votes "for" than "against" will be the materials that will be nominated at the session of the Commission, after consultation between Ministers and the creators of ideas. In addition, critical factors are the existence of non-structural ideas, passive discussion, the low level of involvement by the authors of the ideas (research has shown that almost 35% of the authors participate in later stages) [14], few voices, formal rejection of the proposal by the state administration, lower the level of dialogue between citizens and decision makers etc. The moment when an idea, or a material become included in the next session, the status of the material should clearly show that the debate is following. Upon completion of the process, on the portal, on the part where the material is, it is necessary to enable displaying the status of the material, with a report after the session.

The basic idea of forming such a portal is to facilitate public participation in decision-making processes, giving them the opportunity to propose and discuss new laws using the Internet. Also, it is necessary to facilitate dialogue between citizens and public administration staff, as well as many other relationships that can be established.

In Estonia, there is already a similar portal for creating the environment for eParticipation. In the period from 2001 to 2006, the following results of using such a portal are: it is presented 1140 ideas of which was 64% voted for and 34%

against the idea. 654 proposals was forwarded to the Ministries, from with on the 89% was answered 6% may be implemented, 48% received a negative response and 7% is supported. During this period, some of the proposed topics were: Suggestions for the summer working time, wireless internet marks, downloading the Estonian national anthem from the internet etc.

This method of communication allows to raise the level of development of e-Democracy in terms of [9]:

- Increase of the impact on political decision-making
- Increase in obligations of the state administration to respond to requests from visitors
- Communication between the user (the ability to create common ideas)
- Communication with the state administration
- The ability to track proposals and discussions

In order to implement this kind of solution, besides the infrastructure and IT tools that will be available to citizens, it is necessary to take the following measures [9]:

- Provide constant promotion on the Internet and other media
- Provide a system of e-mail or RSS notification of related discussions by the participants and authors in order to improve the quality and quantity of discussions generated ideas.
- Establish a database of ideas to be signaled previous labeling problems and efforts to simplify the mobility of users.
- Monitoring the progress of ideas once they are directed/delivered to the government

VIII. CONCLUSION

Growth of appropriate development policies and institutions that create and manage these policies is key for building a knowledge economy, the basis of creating the information society and encourage for the development of new technologies for integration and transformation of business processes and management. Institutional change and innovation, as well as innovative technologies that are responsible for transformation from traditional to modern ways of doing business and life in general, are necessary for the proper and efficient management of knowledge, information and communication processes. Specialized institutions and enhanced skills of individuals require that creation, search, acquisition, differentiation and use of these technologies, and their synchronization with the appropriate reform policies, investments, managerial innovations and political revolutions such as the technology become more efficient and effective, in order to create a competitive state, ie. economy of the state based on knowledge.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) are a powerful tool of development and the necessary infrastructure of the knowledge economy. They have a pervasive impact on all human activities, from personal life to business activities and management within the government. ICT speeds up the dissemination of information and knowledge, eliminating geographical restrictions and making information and knowledge accessible. With adequate initial investment, ICT

market entry barriers are significantly reduced, and competition increased. Barriers that appear are usually institutional. Lack of leadership and institutional capacity necessary for the promotion of ICT for business (development) strategies affect the necessity of integrating ICT investment with changes in the organization, processes and skills. The fact is that unless there is a willingness of governments to accept the changes, open market and introduces healthy competition, there is no progress in the development of technology sector. New generations are growing in the digital environment, and the goal is to create conditions to enable them to further develop and use all the models of modern, digital economy.

The transition to eBusiness and e-Government must include all stakeholders: citizens, businesses, public administration, political parties and other organizations and institutions that may contribute to the progress and quality of public administration and to introduction of new technologies in the administration. All this requires major changes to internal procedures of state and local administration, which can be very complicated to implement. The challenge is for the administration to adapt and introduce an innovative way of working, including the healthy and stable relationship with citizens, companies and other organizations and institutions.

There are several factors of which essentially depends the success of e-Government development. First of all, success will depend on the commitment of relevant parties who are responsible for creating and making decisions at certain levels of government and their willingness to fully support these processes. Another critical factor is the human resources/personnel, which is absolutely insufficient for jobs in information technology management. Providing the necessary number and quality of staff to deal with and carry out the process of developing of e-Government, requires special measures and strategies of public authorities in the governmental structures. One of the critical factors is the question of jurisdiction of administrative entities in terms of computerization. It is very important also to create awareness and disseminate knowledge through media promotions, about the possibilities and advantages of information technology management both to the employees in administration and the users (companies and citizens).

In addition, there are other factors that may affect the success of the development and implementation of eGovernment, such as: low general level of digital literacy, lack of adequate legislation and adequate implementation of existing, the transition processes, status and level of development of the private sector etc.

For the future of e-Government and e-Democracy in Montenegro it is very important to use the experience of other countries, with understanding of their successes and failures, and adapting that knowledge to the characteristics of Montenegrin socio-economic environment. In order to make possible for e-Democracy to evolve, in any form, there should be a confidence in the state system, public confidence in public administration but also the confidence of the state in the citizens. In addition, it is necessary to allow everyone under

the same conditions to use the electronic services, because, in that way, it supports the creation of a democratic society.

REFERENCES

- [1] Making IT happen, critical issues on IT management, James D. McKeen and Heather A. Smith, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, England, 2003
- [2] Roadmap for E-Government in the Developing World, 10 Questions E-Government Leaders Should Ask Themselves, The Working Group on E-Government in the Developing World, April 2002
- [3] E-Government – The Digital Divide And Information Sharing: Examining The Issues, Thomas B. Riley, Commonwealth Centre for E-Governance
- [4] E-government More Than An Automation Of Government Services, Information Society Commission, October 2003
- [5] The Transformative Potential of E-Government in Transitional Democracies, Jeffrey W. Seifert, Congressional Research Service, Library of Congress, USA, G. Matthew Bonham, Maxwell School, Syracuse University, USA
- [6] The E-Government Handbook For Developing Countries, Info Dev, Center for Democracy & Technology, November 2002
- [7] Web 2.0. in Government? Why and How?, David Osimo, JRC Scientific and Technical Reports, Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, © European Communities, 2008
- [8] Managing business with electronic Commerce: Issues and Trends, Aryya Gangopadhyay, Copyright © 2002 by Idea Group Publishing
- [9] e-Democracy: Putting Down Global Roots, Janet Caldwell, Institute for Electronic Government, IBM, January, 2004
- [10] Bowling Together: Online Public Engagement in Policy Deliberation, Coleman, Stephen and John Gotze, Hansard Society
- [11] Hearing voices: the experience of online public consultations and discussion in UK governance, Coleman, Stephen, Nicola Hall, et. Al., Nov 2002. Web pages:
- [12] <http://www.epractice.eu/>
- [13] <http://e-democracy.org/>
- [14] <http://interactivedemocracy.blogspot.com/>
- [15] <http://www.publicus.net/ebook/> - eDemocracy eBook: Democracy is Online 2.0